

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad Employees: The Role of Organizational Leadership, Development, And Innovation Commitments

Mr. Najam Uddin Sohu
Government College University, Hyderabad
Email: najam_sohu@yahoo.com

Mr. Hakim Ali Zardari
Segi University, Kota Damasara, Malaysia & Government College University,
Hyderabad, Pakistan
Email: hakimzardari@gmail.com

Syed Junaid Ali
Lincoln University College, Malaysia

Received on: 17-05-2022

Accepted on: 18-06-2022

Abstract

Background: This study aims to be aware of remaining and ascending the university progressive system in a brief time frame because of connection or difficult work and abilities. This review analyzes the presence of legislative issues among state-funded university teachers and their effect on their work fulfillment. Moreover, the review analyzed the effect political discernments have on representative work fulfillment. Consequently, the point of this study was to dissect the impact of the view of authoritative arrangements and their effect on work fulfillment among university educators in Pakistan. This exploration base, comprising of the executives and HR assists them with better advancing their human asset rehearses. What's more, it would help university executives to further develop teacher maintenance and limit turnover. This study would likewise assist universities with the Public Sector Manifesto.

Five parts of occupation fulfillment; notwithstanding generally speaking position fulfillment, work, pay, advancement, compensation, and acknowledgment were inspected. The point of this study was to look at the particular employment fulfillment of public area representatives in Sindh territory. An organized poll overview was conducted. The expected data was gathered from 4 haphazardly chosen public/confidential area authorities from public and confidential universities. The consequence of the review showed that representatives of private universities are happier with compensation, acknowledgment, and working hours than representatives of state-funded universities. Public area laborers are happy with

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

employer stability compared with private area laborers.

Work fulfillment in universities in Hyderabad Pakistan. The city of Hyderabad, which is the second capital of the Sindh area and the second biggest city in the Sindh region, is renowned for its universities. Consequently, a legitimate poll review of 145 teachers was directed to uncover the keen representation of Pakistani grants, the review is novel in that it incorporates models of mathematical and non-mathematical elements that can influence representative fulfillment. Information was examined utilizing multinomial calculated relapse models. Foreseeing conduct fulfillment estimation on a quantitative scale was testing. The outcomes show a more noteworthy fulfillment in confidential universities, which is credited to the workplace, connection to the organization, and compensation. Curiously, well-being and clinical offices, preparing and advancement programs, and institutional arrangements are significant variables that can increment/decline educator fulfillment in the public area.

Keywords: Multinomial Strategic Reversion, Work Fulfillment, Training, Advanced Education, Hyderabad and Pakistan

Introduction

Background:

Various examinations highlight the job that the hierarchical approach plays in introducing representatives both officially and casually (Adams, Ammeter, Treadway, Ferris, Hochvarter, 2002). The utilization of legislative issues in associations is far and wide all through the world and Pakistan is no exception. The impression of hierarchical legislative issues is thought of as uncalled for and one-sided according to a singular's perspective since it addresses the degree to which representatives view the climate in their work environment as a political one that keeps on thinking often about themselves or others (Kacmar and Carlson, 1997). The hierarchical strategy appears as an apparent hierarchical strategy when seen according to a worker's perspective (**Khan, M. S. (2019)**), as it is for the most part thought to be unwanted and characterized as something negative in the working environment. There has been a discussion about the truth of hierarchical legislative issues because of its theoretical nature, making it hard so that the individual might be able to see it as the equivalent, so every individual has their own view of it. Hence, as Ferris et al. (1989) bring up, it ought not to be called hierarchical governmental issues, however, they had been seen as authoritative legislative issues. Given the absence of assets and the insight that people are egotistical commonly, it becomes hard to get away from the results of working environment approaches. Kanter (1979) utilized the term group power, power, and governmental issues as ordinary, and meant it as negative. Power and governmental issues have a critical effect on every part, yet additionally on the whole association. India's way of behaving and demeanor rely upon showing the way of behaving and disposition of different workers, like a partner, managers, and chiefs.

Review of the Literature

The foundation and setting of the review were examined exhaustively, as well as the significance of the review. Also, the review talked about the issue of proclamation and motivation behind the review, the examination questions, the degree and constraint of the review, the reasoning of the review, the fundamental presumptions, and the functional

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

meanings of the key terms utilized in the exploration. The approach was likewise momentarily talked about in the section. The reason for this study was essential to break down the effect of authoritative arrangement discernment and its effect on university personnel work fulfillment in Pakistan.

The writing audit of this study is organized around the idea of legislative issues and their part in the work environment, beginning with the Iliad and Aristotle to the current day. The writing survey tends to the three areas of Organizational Policy Perception (BPS) made by Kamar and Ferris (1991). These include (a) a general political way of behaving, (b) future, and (c) pay and advancement strategy. This study gives free rein to the idea of occupation fulfillment and its relationship with a hierarchical approach with regard to advanced education.

Job Satisfaction:

An enormous number of individuals' personalities are key to their work. In the event that you ask them as a general solicitation what they do; Most of them would answer with the title of their calling. No matter what language they speak in, the vast majority of these individuals have their last name in light of their calling, like pastry specialist, **Khan, M. S 2020.**, accessory, cook, goldsmith, bricklayer, smithy, Taylor, Thatcher. Likewise, a huge piece of the functioning populace would burn through the majority of their 24 hours at work when they are not dozing. Hence, no review would be viewed as complete in the event that this study didn't consider the way that individuals care about their work.

Theoretical framework

The hypothetical system of the review was created and outlined in Figure 1. Utilizing the hypothetical structure, the review shows that the three elements of hierarchical arrangement insight (GP) are first considered by university personnel and afterward their consequences for work fulfillment are investigated. Work fulfillment is examined considering the hypothesis of transformation to work proposed by Dawis, England and Lofquist (1964).

Figure 1: Theoretical framework

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

Methodology

The reason for this study was significant to dissect the impact of impression of authoritative strategies and their effect on work fulfillment among university resources in Pakistan. This study was led to respond to the accompanying examination inquiries alongside the proposed poser :

1. How much do teachers take part in the authoritative approach of state-funded universities?
H. There is an association between strong political gatherings and the endurance of personnel in universities.

2. What is the connection between the hierarchical approach and occupation fulfillment in state-funded universities?

H. There is a huge impact of general political conduct on work fulfillment.

3. How much is the personnel of state-funded universities fulfilled?

H. There is a relationship between the more you walk and the better you progress in the association.

4. How does making it work influence the differentiation in an association?

H. There is a significant relationship between the presentation of compensation and financing rules by the staff and the compensation and advancement strategy laid out in advanced education foundations.

5. How much does an association follow its pay and advancement strategies?

H. There is a critical effect of compensation insight and advancement on work fulfillment.

Sampling

This study followed a blended report technique with an extraordinary methodology. The motivation behind the marvelous methodology is to feature the specific subtleties of how a peculiarity happened and the way things are seen by players in a circumstance. In the human setting, it really implies gathering definite data and bits of knowledge through inductive and subjective strategies, like meetings, conversations, and member perceptions, and applying them according to the perspective of the exploration members.

Questionnaire

A vigorous survey with an excess of 50 inquiries was created subsequent to checking on the important writing. It was additionally assessed by scholastics, analysts, and exploration experts. A pilot venture of 5 meetings was utilized for changes and enhancements to the poll. In the wake of catching respondents with segment data, they were approached to finish five huge areas. The response to most inquiries is recorded on a five-point Likert scale. The classifications of the scale were: High Satisfied, Satisfied, Only OK, Angry, and High Dissatisfied. A few instances of in excess of 50 inquiries are recorded beneath:

1. Sort of business (long-lasting or authoritative)
2. Month-to-month compensation
3. Life coverage Benefits
4. The workplace is helpful
5. Nurturing Assistance
6. Professional preparation

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

7. Clinical offices for spouse/wife and youngsters
8. Learning potential opens doors accessible
9. Available time, and so forth.

Data Collection

A blended technique consolidates quantitative and subjective systems for gathering and showing information in a specific report. Blending different systems presumably started in 1959, when Campbell and Fiske dominated various strategies to represent the authenticity of mental characteristics. They encouraged others to utilize their multi-strategic system to investigate various ways of moving toward information assortment in a review. Utilizing estimations of various characteristics through various procedures, the scientists had the option to make a connection framework known as the multigrain multimethod network. Connection information in the grid could be utilized to make a judgment about the assessed idea of the arranged designs (Khan, M. S. (2022)). A corroborative component examination (CFA) could likewise be utilized to explore the authenticity of designs with officially quantifiable proof. Blended strategies experts consistently use and make different philosophical positions. Green (2007) said that these positions are frequently suggested argumentative places that join post-positive and social constructivist viewpoints, reasonable points of view, and groundbreaking perspectives.

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

Study Analysis

Reliability

The designs utilized for this study had recognized liabilities. Nonetheless, liabilities were reestablished in the neighborhood setting. The worth of Cronbach's alpha should be 0.6 or higher, which is viewed as adequate inward unwavering quality. Cronbach's alpha coefficient values somewhere in the range of 0.6 and 0.7 are viewed as fair dependability, 0.7 to 0.8 as great unwavering quality, and 0.8 to 0.95 as generally excellent dependability (Zikmund et al., 2012; SKP Muhammad, 2023).

Table 1: Reliability of the structures used in the study.

Construct	Mean	Std. Dev	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of items
1. General Political Behavior	2.85	.638	.73	2
2. Go along to get ahead	3.21	.413	.75	7
3. Pay & promotion policies	2.92	.542	.74	6
4. Training	3.05	1.04	.88	3
5. Supervisory Role	3.36	.716	.84	7
6. Input into policies & procedures	3.03	.733	.74	3
7. Meaningfulness of the job	4.06	.521	.71	6
8. Job related Stress	2.54	.750	.80	5
9. Reward system	2.62	.729	.85	4
10. Perception of communicated directives	3.58	.569	.73	3
11. Job satisfaction	3.92	.620	.85	6

Validity Analysis of the Constructs Used in the Study

Since the scale components utilized for this study were created in the Western world, productive legitimacy was likewise reestablished in a neighborhood setting. Legitimacy is an action that really gauges the idea to which it alludes (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Zikmund et al., 2010; MSK Pathan, 2022; MSK Pathan, 2021). Legitimacy is not entirely settled by happy legitimacy (Bryman and Chime, 2011; MS Pathan, 2022) and built legitimacy (Zikmund et al., 2010). Valuable legitimacy is of two sorts prejudicial and merged legitimacy (Campbell and Fiske, 1959).

Convergent Validity

The degree to which the action meets or is enhanced by different proportions of a similar constructor is called union legitimacy (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

Discriminant Validity

The square foundation of the announced general distinction (factorial burden) is more prominent than the square of every relationship pair, affirming the prejudicial legitimacy of the designs (Hair Jr. et al., 2015). The valuable legitimacy of the designs utilized in this paper was laid out by an exploratory and corroborative examination of the variable and considering the way that different specialists have likewise approved the designs beforehand in a similar setting.

Results and Findings

Table 2: Discriminatory operation of the construction used in the study.

	GPB	GAGA	PPP	Tr	SR	IPP	MoJ	JRS	RS	PCD	JS
GPB	0.76										
GAGA	0.04	0.81									
PPP	0.002	0.04	0.84								
Tr	0.005	0.45	0.06	0.9							
SR	0.05	0.005	0.04	0.60	0.86						
IPP	0.01	0.006	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.87					
MoJ	0.04	0.006	0.05	0.05	0.14	0.01	0.86				
JRS	0.008	0.002	0.01	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.08	0.89			
RS	0.10	0.012	0.01	0.10	0.14	0.09	0.0025	0.057	0.83		
PCD	0.006	0.016	0.005	0.09	0.12	0.02	0.14	0.003	0.04	0.76	
JS	0.022	0.006	0.003	0.012	0.026	0.015	0.37	0.11	0.05	0.14	0.9

Model:

The model: For the treatment of the reaction variable, which is typically a polarity in calculated relapse, we say that the reaction variable can expect a worth of 1 with the likelihood of progress (π) or a worth of 0 with the likelihood of disappointment (π). Such factors are called Bernoulli factors. Known as multinomial or polytomy, Tabachnick and Fidell (1996) utilize the term polypectomy. Prescient factors in strategic relapse can take any structure persistently or subjectively. In this manner, there is no sign of the conveyance of the indicator factors. They don't flaunt that they are normally straightly associated or conveyed with a similar fluctuation inside each gathering. Capability in calculated relapse, as opposed to the strategic relapse capability, which is the logit change of the π :

$$\pi = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where are β_0 constants of equations and β is the coefficients of independent variables?

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

$$\log it[\pi(x_i)] = \log\left[\frac{\pi(x)}{1-\pi(x)}\right] = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \dots + \beta_i \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Descriptive statistics

Overall political behavior has a significant impact on job satisfaction.

Table 3: Total factor of political behavior

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized		t	Sig
	Coefficients		Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	4.248	0.147			28.91	0.00
GPB	0.154	0.050	-.159		-3.07	0.00

(R2 = 0.25, adjusted R2 = 0.022, F (1.365) = 9.412, P

The aftereffects of the relapse show that the indicator of the general political way of behaving (M=2.85, SD=0.638) makes sense of 2.5% of the deviation of the reliant variable work fulfillment (R2= 0.025, F (1,365) = 9.412, p<0.05). It likewise shows that the impact of by and large political way of behaving ($\beta = - 0.159$) on work fulfillment (M = 3.92, SD = 0.620) is genuinely critical. In this way, the scientist expects that there is a critical impact of general political conduct on work fulfillment.

Conclusion

This study reasons that governmental issues exist in practically all associations and spots of learning are no exemption. With regard to governmental issues, Faculty individuals act similarly as representatives of different establishments. The administration of advanced education establishments could check out this present circumstance and better deal with their separate foundations by smoothing out their arrangements, specifically their HR approaches. Research by Vigoda-Gado (2003); Muhammad, S. K. P. (2023) reasoned that workers consider workplace issues to be a method for making individual increases to the detriment of different representatives, regardless of whether that gain comes to the detriment of the whole association.

Recommendations

- Most importantly, it is suggested that HR the board and divisions execute and acknowledge the presence of strategies in their particular establishments. Without embracing this situation, they cannot support or form their staff strategy. Senior administration likewise needs to concentrate on this point exhaustively to understand what's genuinely going on with authoritative arrangement. Without information and understanding, they cannot make a difference.
- It is likewise suggested that the administration understand that legislative issues is very nearly a lifestyle and that they can't kill it totally, however, can attempt to limit it. This understanding will show them the way forward.
- HR divisions ought to think about holes that exist or could emerge because of a

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

strategy, and ought to make and form strategies that consider the socioeconomics of their specific establishment. It is additionally suggested that the Higher Education Committee be careful in planning and scattering strategy rules to the foundations concerned. It should foster a framework that gives straightforwardness. Then again, the HEC should thoroughly inspect the administration of the organizations to guarantee that the approach rules they lay out are met.

Limitations

There are a few limits in this study that ought to be reflected in the preparation of future examinations regarding ideas and systems. There are a few individual and hierarchical qualities that need more examination to empower a superior comprehension of workforce political conduct inside the assessment framework.

References

1. Agresti, An Introduction to Categorical Data Analysis, 2nd Ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 2007.
2. Adams, G. L., Ammeter, A. P., Treadway, D. C., Ferris, G. R., Hochwarter, W. A., & Kolinsky, R.W. (2002). Perceptions of organizational politics: Additional thoughts, reactions, and multi-level issues. *Research in Multi-Level Issues*, 1, 287- 294.
3. Alderson et al, "Social status and cultural consumption in the United States", 2007.
4. Allen, N.J. & Meyer, J.P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology* 63.
5. Andrews, M. C., & Kacmar, K.M. (2001). Discriminating among organizational politics, justice, and support. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 22, 347-366.
6. Archive & Records Association (ARA) (2018). Code of Ethics. Retrieved from: <https://www.archives.org.uk/membership/code-of-ethics.html> (Accessed: 25 December 2018).
7. Ashford, S.J., Lee, C., & Bobko, P. (1989). Content causes and consequences of job insecurity: a theory-based measure and substantive test. *Academy of Management Journal*, 32(4), 803-829. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/256569>
8. Baker, George, P., Michael, G., & Bengt, H. (1994).The wage policy of a firm. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109, 921-955.
9. Bartel, Anne P. (1981). "Race Differences in Job Satisfaction: A Reappraisal," *Journal of Human Resources* 16: 295 – 303.
10. Bauer, "Sexual Behavior and Drug Use among Asian and Latino Adolescents", 2006.
11. Bellemare, Charles and Bruce S. Shearer. (2006). "Sorting, Incentives and Risk Preferences: Evidence from a Field Experiment." IZA Discussion Paper No. 2227, Bonn.
12. Benabou, Roland and Jean Tirole. (2003). "Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation." *Review of Economic Studies* 70: 489 – 520.
13. Bernhardt, D., & Scoones, D. (1993). Promotion, turnover, and preemptive wage offer. *American Economic Review*, 83(4), 771-791.
14. Block, P. (1988). *The empowered manager: positive political skills at work* San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
15. Blood, G.W., Ridenour, J.S., Thomas, E.A., Qualls, C.D., & Hammer, C.Sch. (2002). Predicting job satisfaction among speech-language pathologists working in public schools. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 33, 282-290.
16. Bowles, S., H. Gintis and M. Osborne. (2001). "The Determinants of Earnings: A Behavioral Approach," *Journal of Economic Literature* 39: 1137 – 76.

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

17. Bravendam Research Incorporated (2002). Effective management through measurement: Special report. Retrieved from the World Wide Web on December 15, 2010 from <http://www.employeesatisfactions.com/>
18. Brink, H. (1996). Fundamentals of research methodology for health care professionals. Cape Town: Juta.
19. Brink, JB & Wood, MJ. (1998). Advanced designs in nursing research. 2nd edition.
20. British Educational Research Association (BERA) (2018). Ethical guidelines for educational research. Retrieved from: <https://www.bera.ac.uk/researchersresources/publications/ethical-guidelines> -for-educational-research-2018 (Accessed: 25 December 2018).
21. Brown, M. (2001). "Unequal Pay, Unequal Responses? Pay Referents and their Implications for Pay Level Satisfaction," Journal of Management Studies 38: 879 – 96.
22. Bryman, A. (2001). Social Research Methods. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
23. Bryman, A., undated, 'Triangulation' available at <http://www.qualityresearchinternational.com/socialresearch/triangulation.htm> (Accessed: 25 August 2017).
24. Burns, N. & Grove, SK. (1997). The Practice of Nursing Research Conduct, Critique, & Utilization. 3rd edition. Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders and Co.
25. Burns, T. E. (1961). The management of innovation. University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign's Academy for Entrepreneurial Leadership Historical Research Reference in Entrepreneurship.
26. Byrne, Z.S. (2005). Fairness reduces the negative effects of organizational politics on turnover intentions: Citizenship behavior and job performance. J. Bus. Psychol., 20, 175-200.
27. C. Oclay, "The Burnout in Nursing Academicians in Turkey", International journal of nursing studies, Vol. 38, No. 1, 2001, Pp. 201-208.
28. Camp, S. D. (1994). Assessing the effects of organizational commitment and job satisfaction on turnover: An event history approach. The Prison Journal, 74(3), 279–305.
29. Campbell, Donald, and D. Fiske. 1959. Convergent and discriminant validation by the multitrait-multimethod matrix. Psychological Bulletin 56.2 (March): 81–105.
30. Carmichael, L. (1983). Firm-specific human capital and promotion ladders. Bell Journal of Economics, 14, 251-258.
31. Chang, C. H., Rosen, C. C., & Levy, P. E. (2009).The relationship between perceptions of organizational politics and employee attitudes, strain, and behavior. A meta-analytic examination. Academy of Management Journal, 52:779-801
32. Chang, C. H., Rosen, C. C., & Levy, P. E. (2009).The relationship between perceptions of organizational politics and employee attitudes, strain, and behavior. A meta-analytic examination. Academy of Management Journal, 52:779-801
33. Chang, C. H., Rosen, C. C., & Levy, P. E. (2009).The relationship between perceptions of organizational politics and employee attitudes, strain, and behavior. A meta-analytic examination. Academy of Management Journal, 52:779-801
34. Chang, M.L. (2009). An appraisal perspective of teacher burnout: Examining the emotional work of teachers. Educational Psychology Review, 21, 193-218.
35. Chew, Howe and Z. Liaolay, "Family Structures on Income and Career Satisfaction of Managers in Singapore", Journal of Management Development, Vol. 18, No. 5, 1999, Pp. 464-476.
36. Clark, A. E., & Oswald, A. J. (1996).Satisfaction and comparison income. Journal of Public Economics, 61, 359-381.
37. Cohen, L. Manion, L. & Morrison K. (2000). Research Methods in Education. London: Routledge Falmer.
38. Comber, B., & Nixon, H. (2009). Teachers' work and pedagogy in an area of accountability.

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

- Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education, 30(3), 333-345.
39. Corbetta, P. (2003). *Social Research Theory, Methods, and Techniques*. London: SAGE Publications.
 40. Creswell, J.W. (1998). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design Choosing Among Five Traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
 41. Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A. A., & Toth, P. (1997). The relationship of organizational politics and support to work behaviors, attitudes, and stress. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 18, 159–180.
 42. Cropanzano, R.S. Kacmar. K.M. & Bozeman, D.P. (1995). Organizational politics, justice, and support: Their differences and similarities. In R. S. Cropanzano & K.M. Kacmar (Eds.) (pp. 1-18), *Organizational politics. Justice and support: Managing social climate at work*. Westport, CT: Quorum Books.
 43. D.W. Hosmer and J.S. Lemeshow, *Applied Logistic Regression*, 2nd Ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 2000.
 44. David, B., & Wesson, T. (2001). A comparative analysis among public versus private sector professionals. *The Innovation Journal*, 19 (15), 28-45.
 45. David, M. & Sutton C.D. (2004). *Social Research the Basics*. London: SAGE Publications.
 46. De Nobile, J.J., & McCormick, J. (2005). Job satisfaction and occupational stress in catholic primary schools. A paper presented at the Annual Conference of the Australian Association for Research in Education, Sydney, November 27th– December 1st, 2005.
 47. F.J. Lacy and B.A. Shaheen, “Job Satisfaction among Academic Staff: An International Perspective”, *Higher Education*, Vol. 34, No. 3, 1997, Pp. 305-322
 48. H. Motoko, Howard, and M. Homma, “Job Satisfaction of Japanese Career Women and its Influence on Turnover Intention”, *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol. 4, 2001, Pp 23-38.
 49. J.A. Jacob and Sarah, “The Academic Life Course, Time Pressures and Gender inequality”, *Community, Work & Family*, Vol. 7, No. 2, 2004, Pp. 143–161.
 50. J.F. Volkwein and K. Parmley, “Comparing Administrative Satisfaction in Public and Private Universities”, *Research in Higher Education*, Vol. 41, No. 1, 2000, Pp. 95-217
 51. J.K. Dua, “Job Stressors and their Effects on Physical Health, Emotional Health, and Job Satisfaction in a University”, *Journal of Educational Administration*, Vol. 32, No. 1, 1994, Pp. 59-78
 52. K. Ssesanga and R.M. Garrett, “Job satisfaction of University Academics: Perspectives from Uganda”, *Higher Education*, Vol. 50, 2005, Pp. 33–56.
 53. Khan, M. S., Rahpoto, M. S., & Mangnejo, G. M. (2020). The Effect of the Financial Crisis on Corporal Well-Being: Apparent Impact Matters: Assessment of Contagion to Developing Economies. *Research Journal of Social Sciences and Economics Review*, 1(3), 232-238.
 54. Khan, M. S., Rahpoto, M. S., & Talpur, U. (2021). The Effect of the Financial Crisis on Corporal Wellbeing: Apparent Impact Matters. In *Internet of Everything and Big Data* (pp. 25-34). CRC Press.
 55. Khoso, A. A. K., Pathan, M. S. K., & Ahmed, M. (2022). Exploring The Impacts and Aftershocks of Covid-19 on Islamic Banking and Conventional Banking in Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 179-192.
 56. Khowaja, I. A., Talpur, U., Soomro, S. H., & Khan, M. S. (2021). The non-banking financial institutions in perspective of economic growth of Pakistan. *Applied Economics Letters*, 28(8), 701-706.
 57. M.E. Ward and J.S. Peter, “Job Satisfaction among Male and Female Academic Employees of

Analyzing Job Satisfaction Among Government College University Hyderabad...

- Scottish Universities”, *Scottish Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 47 No.3, 2000, Pp. 273-304.
58. Memon, A. R., Shaikh, E., & Khan, M. S. (2019). Determination of customer satisfaction of Hyderabad restaurants. *Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science and Research (IIJSR)*, 3(3), 11-18.
59. Memon, A., & Khan, M. S. (2019). Impact of Pay on Job Satisfaction in Business Organizations. *Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS)(Peer Reviewed International Journal)*, 3(3), 69-74.
60. Muhammad, S. K. P. (2023). The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Commitment and Turnover Intentions: A Study of The Importance of Positive Culture for Retaining Employees. *Global Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences (GRJMSS)*, 1(1), 85-94.
61. O. Titus and C. Hickson, “Some Aspects of Overall Job Satisfaction: A Binomial Logit Model”, *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 18, No. 4, 2003, Pp 357- 367.
62. O. Titus, “Personal Correlates of Job Satisfaction: Empirical evidence from UK Universities”, *International Journal of Social Economics*, Vol. 30, No. 12, 2003, Pp. 1210-1232.
63. Online Statistical Information Unit of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan. www.hec.gov.pk
64. P. Ghinetti, “The Public–Private Job Satisfaction Differential in Italy”, *Labour*, Vol. 21, No. 2, 2007, Pp. 361-388.
65. Pathan, M. S. K. (2022). The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Leadership Effectiveness. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1-7.
66. Pathan, M. S. K. (2022). The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Commitment and Turnover Intentions. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 34-43.
67. Pathan, M. S. K. (2023). Assessing the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between organizational culture and employee commitment. *International Research Journal of Education and Innovation*, 4(1), 1-11.
68. Pathan, M. S. K., Khoso, A. A., & Ahmed, M. (2022). Digital Model Anecdotes Through Artificial Intelligence in Socioeconomic and Islamic Investments. *International Research Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3(2), 195-209.
69. Rahat, S., & Pathan, M. S. K. (2021). Sustainable Climate Approach and in Context of Environment Economy: A Classical Analyze Matters. *Neutron*, 21(1), 40-45.
70. S.P. Deshpande, “Factors Influencing Employee Association”, *The Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 129, No. 6, 1995, Pp.621-628.
71. Schemp et al, “Maternal age and parity-associated risks of preterm birth: differences by race/ethnicity”, 2007.
72. SPSS (2010). *Statistical package for social sciences*. (Version. 17.00). SPSS Inc.
73. T. Oshagbemi, “Job Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction in Higher Education”, *Education + Training*, Vol. 39, No. 9, 1997, Pp. 354-359.